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Dialogic Speech and its Methodology for Development in Children

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***Abstract:** This article addresses the concept of dialogic speech, how to develop it, and the methodologies for developing dialogic speech in children.*

***Keywords:** dialogic speech, communication, ability, thought, skill, empathy, role, situation, competence.*

Introduction

Dialogic speech is the process of communication based on the exchange of ideas, interaction, and understanding between people. Dialogic speech is important for children as it ensures the development of their social skills, thinking, problem-solving abilities, and emotional development.

The main objectives of developing dialogic speech in children are:

1. Helping children express and understand thoughts.
2. Developing children's communication skills.
3. Fostering empathy and communication culture.
4. Encouraging critical thinking.

Methodologies for Developing Dialogic Speech in Children

1. **Role Play:** Children can describe various situations through play. This method helps develop communication skills.
2. **Question-Answer Method:** Teachers can ask children questions, encouraging the exchange of ideas and the development of expressive skills.
3. **Temporary Groups:** Children can be divided into small groups to ask each other questions and share ideas. This method fosters social skills.

4. Classroom Communication: Creating opportunities during class for children to express their thoughts and communicate with one another.
5. Art and Creative Work: Giving children opportunities to express their thoughts by writing stories, reciting poems, or drawing.

Results:

By applying these methodologies, children can develop the ability to express their thoughts clearly, master dialogic speech, and become prepared for social communication.

The methodologies for developing dialogic speech:

Help develop social skills (communication, listening, understanding).

Enhance the ability to express ideas clearly and coherently.

Encourage critical thinking and creativity.

Aid in developing a communication culture.

By effectively applying these methods, children will develop the necessary skills to master dialogic speech and succeed in mutual communication.

Dialog is the primary form of interaction between children, adults, and peers. In kindergartens, teaching takes place in two forms: a) in free speech communication; b) during special lessons. Dialog more often occurs in free speech communication and is the foundation for naturally enriching children's vocabulary, improving pronunciation skills, and developing fluent speech skills. In special lessons, dialog is taught once or twice a month.

While in kindergarten, children engage in free communication with the teacher and other children. At home, adults should engage children in dialog on various topics. Teaching dialogic speech (or oral speech) usually takes the form of conversation, i.e., exchanging thoughts between adults and children or between children themselves.

In repetitive and summarizing conversations, the teacher uses various methods to teach children to analyze, compare, complete, and deepen their understanding of what they have seen, organizing their knowledge and encouraging them to draw conclusions.

Control conversations are conducted by the teacher to assess children's knowledge on a previously covered topic. Using questions, the teacher can determine the level of knowledge gained during the learning process. The teacher uses both unplanned and planned conversations when working with children.

Unplanned conversations (used specifically for children, as they are unaware of what will be discussed) can take place during routine activities or various child activities such as games or labor. The teacher must always be prepared for any type of communication, relying on their professional training. A significant part of the teacher's role is organizing meaningful conversations with children to teach them their native language.

In spontaneous conversations that arise out of the necessity for communication, the teacher does not prepare the grammatical structure or phonological aspects of their speech but must still be prepared for the topic of the conversation.

Planned conversations are prepared beforehand. In these, the teacher prepares children by directing their attention to topics related to future conversations, focusing on familiar aspects of the world

around them. The structure of the conversation depends on the topic and the children's age, but every conversation generally includes three components: 1) introduction; 2) development of the topic; 3) conclusion.

Therefore, dialogic speech in preschool institutions is developed and refined through structured conversations.

Conclusion

Thus, dialogic speech plays an important role in a child's life not only in developing communicative skills but also in social, emotional, and intellectual growth. It is necessary to focus on developing this ability in sick children and young people, as it helps them express their thoughts and establish stronger connections.

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